

DIGITAL BUSINESS MODELS, ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN SELECTED SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: This study examined digital business models, entrepreneurship, and supply chain management in selected small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction as well as investigate the relationship between networking and inventory turnover in small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 150 owners of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State. The hypotheses were tested with the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Findings showed a statistically significant positive relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction, it further revealed a positive relationship between networking and inventory turnover among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State. This study conclusively established a strong, statistically significant positive relationship between digital business models, entrepreneurship, and effective supply chain management among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. It was recommended that Anambra State SMEs need to adopt mobile commerce by integrating mobile payments, logistics tracking, and e-commerce platforms to reduce lead times and boost efficiency. Also, Anambra State SMEs need to cultivate strategic networking through conferences, workshops, and industry associations to enhance inventory turnover and boost business performance.

Keywords: Digital Business Models, Entrepreneurship, Supply Chain Management, Mobile Commerce, Networking, Lead Time Reduction, and Inventory Turnover.

INTRODUCTION

Digital technology has revolutionized the business landscape, creating innovative digital business models that transform how companies operate, interact with customers, and create value (Awawdeh, Abulaila, Alshanty & Alzoubi, 2022). Digital business models leverage cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, mobile commerce, networking, and the Internet of Things to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and increase competitiveness. These models enable businesses to adapt to shifting market demands, exploit new opportunities, and navigate complex global markets (Olawale & Devi, 2023). Successful digital business models, such as platform-based and subscription-based models, have disrupted traditional industries and created new avenues for growth. According to Dibie et al. (2019) and Philemon and Chinelo (2024), innovation is predicated on the development of new technological advancements that flow into

new combinations of current technology and the application of newly acquired knowledge by the organization (Philemon & Chinelo (2024). The inability of Businesses to keep up with the ever-evolving tech landscape leads to concerns over obsolescence and loss of competitiveness (Smith et al., 2022; Ezeanokwasa, Nwagbala, Nwachukwu, Oranusi & Ani, 2023). Access to financing can be improved by promoting the use of financial technologies, particularly for small and medium-sized businesses (Nkiruka, Chinelo, Raphael, Nwadiogo & Ejike, 2023). However, the effectiveness of digital business models relies heavily on entrepreneurial capabilities, which involve identifying and capitalizing on opportunities, managing risk, and driving innovation. Effective entrepreneurship is crucial for unlocking the potential of digital business models (Faloye & Owoeye, 2023).

Supply chain management (SCM) plays a vital role in ensuring the seamless operation of businesses, from raw material sourcing to end-product delivery. SCM involves coordinating and integrating various activities, including logistics, procurement, inventory management, and distribution (Zekhnini, Cherrafi, Bouhaddou, Benghabrit & Garza-Reyes, 2021). In today's global market, businesses face different challenges in their efforts to compete, hence, organizations must identify the importance of supply chain management (SCM) practices that improve their firm performance and coordinate with their supply chain partners to promote their joint performance as stated in (Miracle, Christian, & Stella, 2024). Effective supply chain management enables businesses to reduce costs, enhance customer satisfaction, and gain a competitive edge (Pournader, Ghaderi, Hassanzadegan & Fahimnia, 2021). In today's fast-paced and globalized market, supply chain resilience and agility are critical for responding to disruptions, managing risk, and capitalizing on opportunities. Supply chain management strategies, such as just-in-time and total quality management, can significantly impact business performance. However, small and medium enterprises often face unique supply chain challenges that hinder their ability to compete with larger corporations (Wieland, 2021).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of the Nigerian economy. Small and Medium Businesses contribute meaningfully to economic development and job creation in Nigeria (Ajibola, 2020; Nkiruka, Chinelo, Raphael, Nwadiogo & Ejike, 2023). In Anambra State particularly, where they contribute significantly to employment, economic growth, and poverty reduction. SMEs in Anambra State operate in various sectors, including manufacturing, services, and agriculture (Okoli, 2024). However, these enterprises face numerous challenges, including limited access to finance, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient managerial expertise. Chinelo, Francisca, and Joelin (2023) Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) are businesses with relatively limited resources, including capital, workforce, and operational scope, compared to large corporations. SMEs cover a wide range of industries and sectors, including manufacturing, services, retail, and technology startups. Due to their size, SMEs are often more adaptable and responsive to market demands, which contributes to local economic development (Hisrich, Peters & Shepherd, 2017; Nwagbala, Ezeanokwasa & Johnson, 2023). These challenges hinder their ability to adopt innovative digital business models and effective supply chain management strategies, ultimately affecting their competitiveness and sustainability. This study evaluates the intersection of digital business models, entrepreneurship, and supply chain management in selected SMEs in Anambra State. Specifically, this research will examine the impact of mobile commerce, networking, lead time reduction, and inventory turnover on SME performance. By exploring these critical variables, this study offers valuable insights into how SMEs in Anambra State can leverage digital business models and supply chain management to drive growth and competitiveness.

Statement of the Problem

This study is required because the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State encounter many obstacles to their expansion, sustainability, and competitiveness. These businesses suffer from weak management experience, restricted access to capital, inadequate infrastructure, and poor uptake of digital technology, all of

which contribute to operational inefficiencies. In particular, SMEs in Anambra State struggle with poor mobile commerce strategies that prevent them from taking advantage of the sizable mobile market; poor networking that prevents them from forming important business alliances and connections; and ineffective supply chain management that leads to excessive inventory turnover and lengthy lead times, wasting money and missing out on opportunities.

Furthermore, the lack of innovative digital business models and entrepreneurial capabilities exacerbates these challenges, constraining SMEs' ability to compete with larger corporations. If left unaddressed, these challenges will continue to stifle SME growth, perpetuate poverty, and hinder economic development in Anambra State. This study aims to bridge the existing knowledge gap by investigating the impact of mobile commerce, networking, lead time reduction, and inventory turnover on SME performance, providing valuable insights into how these enterprises can leverage digital business models and supply chain management to drive growth and competitiveness, ultimately contributing to the socio-economic development of Anambra State and mitigating the negative consequences of stagnated SME growth, including unemployment, reduced economic activity, and decreased government revenue.

Objectives of the Study

This study is required because the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State encounter many obstacles to their expansion, sustainability, and competitiveness. These businesses suffer from weak management experience, restricted access to capital, inadequate infrastructure, and poor uptake of digital technology, all of which contribute to operational inefficiencies. In particular, SMEs in Anambra State struggle with poor mobile commerce strategies that prevent them from taking advantage of the sizable mobile market; poor networking that prevents them from forming important business alliances and connections; and ineffective supply chain management that leads to excessive inventory turnover and lengthy lead times, wasting money and missing out on opportunities.

Furthermore, the lack of innovative digital business models and entrepreneurial capabilities exacerbates these challenges, constraining SMEs' ability to compete with larger corporations. If left unaddressed, these challenges will continue to stifle SME growth, perpetuate poverty, and hinder economic development in Anambra State. This study aims to bridge the existing knowledge gap by investigating the impact of mobile commerce, networking, lead time reduction, and inventory turnover on SME performance, providing valuable insights into how these enterprises can leverage digital business models and supply chain management to drive growth and competitiveness, ultimately contributing to the socio-economic development of Anambra State and mitigating the negative consequences of stagnated SME growth, including unemployment, reduced economic activity, and decreased government revenue.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction in small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between networking and inventory turnover in small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction in small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between networking and inventory turnover in small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Business Owners

This study provides insights for SME owners to enhance operations, improve efficiency, and increase competitiveness through digital business models and supply chain optimization.

Government

The study informs policy decisions to promote SME growth, entrepreneurship, and economic development in Anambra State, highlighting areas for policy support and intervention.

Customers

Customers will benefit from improved SME efficiency, enhanced product/service offerings, reduced prices, and faster delivery times, accelerating satisfaction and loyalty.

Academics

This study offers a foundation for future SME management research and education. In addition to adding to our understanding of supply chain management, entrepreneurship, and digital business models

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Digital Business Models

Digital business models represent a transformative shift in the way companies generate, hand over, and express value in the digital age (Faloye & Owoeye, 2023). From a strategic perspective, digital business models enable organizations to leverage technology to innovate, disrupt, and re-imagine traditional industries. They facilitate the development of new revenue streams, enhance customer engagement, and improve operational efficiency (Awawdeh, Abulaila, Alshanty & Alzoubi, 2022). Digital business models also enable companies to monetize data, foster collaboration, and drive ecosystem growth. Various forms of digital business models exist, including platform-based, subscription-based, freemium, and data-driven models, each offering distinct benefits and challenges (Olawale & Devi, 2023). According to Audu and Nwagbala (2024) The information and communication technology-driven global corporate world of today has transformed the business world into a global village. For the organization to succeed its strategy must be great, focused, and sharp (Audu & Nwagbala, 2024).

The digital business models incorporate technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT) blockchain, and artificial intelligence, to refurbish core business processes. They enable real-time data analysis, predictive insights, and automated decision-making (David-West, Iheanachor & Umukoro, 2020). Digital business models also prioritize user experience, convenience, and personalization, leading to increased customer loyalty and retention. Moreover, they facilitate strategic partnerships, collaborations, and open innovation, allowing companies to stay agile and adaptable in rapidly changing markets (Khairuddin & Olowosuyi, 2020). Effective digital business models require a deep understanding of customer needs, market trends, and technological advancements, as well as a willingness to experiment, iterate, and continuously innovate. Organizations can unlock new growth opportunities, thrive in the digital economy and drive competitiveness, by embracing digital business models, (Olaolu, 2022).

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in Nigeria's economic development, with small and medium enterprises (SMEs) being substantial contributors. However, sustaining these businesses poses constraints that need a comprehensive exploration (Nkiruka, Chinelo, Raphael, Nwadiogo & Ejike, 2023). Entrepreneurship incorporates the process of capitalizing on opportunities, identifying, driving innovation, and creating value through resource mobilization and strategic risk-taking. It includes the capacity to forecast the future and overcome uncertainty and ambiguity with adaptability and resilience (Diandra & Azmy, 2020). It extends over a unique blend of strategic thinking, creative problem-solving, and collaborative leadership, encouraging a culture of experimentation, learning, and continuous improvement. Individuals and teams can transform markets, industries, and communities, generating employment, economic growth, and social impact through entrepreneurial ventures, (Rosário, Raimundo & Cruz, 2022).

There are many different types of entrepreneurship; social, technological, and sustainable entrepreneurship are a few examples that each address particular societal demands and issues. Individuals and organizations may unleash their creative potential, spur growth, and prosper in the quickly changing business environment of today by adopting entrepreneurial mindsets and abilities (Prince, Chapman & Cassey, 2021).

Mobile Commerce

Mobile commerce (m-commerce) represents the convergence of wireless technology, internet connectivity, and commerce, enabling consumers to conduct financial transactions, access services, and purchase products using mobile devices (Chopdar & Balakrishnan, 2020). M-commerce has transformed the retail landscape, providing unparalleled convenience, accessibility, and personalization. Through mobile apps, mobile-optimized websites, and text-based services, businesses can reach customers anywhere, anytime, offering tailored experiences and real-time engagement (Liao & Yang, 2020). M-commerce facilitates various activities, including mobile payments, banking, shopping, and ticketing, streamlining transactions, and enhancing user experience. As mobile device penetration and internet adoption continue to grow, m-commerce is increasingly vital for businesses seeking to expand their market reach, drive sales, and stay competitive in the digital economy (Kao & L'Huillier, 2022).

Networking

Networking involves the creation, maintenance, and utilization of relationships between individuals, organizations, or entities to achieve mutual benefits, share resources, and exchange information (Albourini, Ahmad, Abuhashesh & Nusairat, 2020). Defined broadly, networking encompasses social, professional, and business connections that facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and access to opportunities (Elfring, Klyver & Burg, 2021). In a business context, networking refers to the establishment of strategic partnerships, alliances, and supply chain relationships to enhance competitiveness and drive growth (Anwar & Ali-Shah, 2020). From a technological perspective, networking involves the interconnection of devices, systems, and infrastructure to enable data communication and exchange. Social networking, meanwhile, focuses on personal relationships and community building through platforms like social media (Zheng, Ahsan & DeNoble, 2020). Professional networking, exemplified by associations and conferences, aims to foster expertise sharing and career advancement. Ultimately, networking enables individuals and organizations to leverage collective strengths, expertise, and resources to achieve shared goals and success (Olanrewaju, Hossain, Whiteside & Mercieca, 2020).

Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management (SCM) is the organization of activities, resources, and partners to produce and deliver products or services from raw materials to end customers (Craighead, Ketchen & Darby, 2020). SCM encompasses a range of processes, including sourcing, procurement, production planning, inventory management, logistics, transportation, and distribution. It ensures the seamless distribution of information, goods, and services along the value chain, decreasing costs, and risks, and improving customer satisfaction (Zekhnini, Cherrafi, Bouhaddou, Benghabrit & Garza-Reyes, 2021). Business firms also gain stronger market positions with better earnings when concentrating more on integrated supply chains (Nakasumi, 2017; Obasi, Ojiaku & Nwagbala, 2024).

From a strategic perspective, supply chain management involves aligning organizational goals with supply chain objectives, fostering collaboration and communication among stakeholders, and leveraging technology to drive efficiency and visibility. SCM also covers managing supply chain risks, ensuring sustainability and social responsibility, and adapting to changing market demands and customer needs (Wieland, 2021). Various supply chain models exist, including just-in-time, total quality management, and vendor-managed inventory, each tailored to specific industry requirements and business goals. Organizations can attain a competitive edge, enhance profitability, and foster resilience in a complex and dynamic business environment by improving supply chain operations (Alzoubi, Ghazal, Sahawneh & Al-Kassem, 2022).

Lead Time Reduction

Lead time reduction pertains to the process of decreasing the duration between receiving a customer order and delivering the product or service. It is also defined as the time elapsed from the beginning to the end of a production process or project (Srouf & Azmy, 2021). Lead time reduction is the acceleration of the period required for materials or products to move from supplier to manufacturer to customer (Suri, 2020). It is the decrease of the period enabling faster production and delivery (Boysen, Fedtke & Schwerdfeger, 2021). Lead time reduction can be viewed as the period between ordering and receipt of goods or services, highlighting the importance of efficient procurement and inventory management. By decreasing lead time, businesses can enhance responsiveness, agility, and customer satisfaction (Barman & Mahata, 2022).

Inventory Turnover

The number of times an organization sells and replaces its inventory in a specific time frame is known as inventory turnover. According to Nasution (2020), it can also be defined as the ratio of average inventory value to cost of goods sold. Inventory turnover is a term used in accounting to describe how well a business manages its stock, showing how rapidly items are sold and replaced. It represents the rate at which inventory flows through the supply chain in logistics. Inventory turnover, which emphasizes the necessity for ideal stock levels, is operationally defined as the frequency of inventory replenishment (Wajo, 2021). It affects cash flow financially since quicker turnover lowers storage and maintenance expenses. On the other hand, inventory turnover can be considered a measure of how well the supply chain functions, how much demand there is for a product, and how much a company can charge before losing customers or becoming less competitive (Eryatna, Eltivia & Handayawati, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Supply Chain Resilience Theory by David Closs and Thomas Goldsby (2007). This theory emphasizes the importance of building robust and adaptable supply chains capable of withstanding

disruptions. This involves identifying potential risks and vulnerabilities, developing mitigation strategies, and fostering collaborative relationships with suppliers and stakeholders (Ivanov, 2021). Supply chain resilience integrates flexibility, agility, and adaptability to quickly respond to disruptions, ensuring continuity and minimizing impact. By investing in supply chain visibility and monitoring, companies can proactively manage risks, enhance customer satisfaction, and maintain competitiveness. This theory is relevant to the study because it can inform SMEs in Anambra State, on building adaptive supply chains to mitigate digital business risks and operational disruptions.

Empirical Studies

Olawale and Devi (2023) investigated on adequate digital firms, management, and entrepreneurship in Nigeria as the index in the post-pandemic era. The study adopted a qualitative approach with semi-structured interviews. The participants recruited were 18. The results of the thematic analysis indicated entrepreneurs adopting digital technologies.

Faloye and Owoeye (2023) explored the performance of small and micro firms in Nigeria: the study sought to know the mediating role of entrepreneurial orientation. A survey research design is used in this study. Data were gathered from 142 MSEs specifically chosen to operate in Ondo State, Nigeria. The outcomes showed that BMI significantly impacted the MSEs' performance. A significant correlation between EO and a firm's performance was observed. A strong positive correlation between EO and BMI exists. Furthermore, this study demonstrated that EO mediates the association between a firm's success and its BMI.

Awawdeh, Abulaila, Alshanty, and Alzoubi (2022) evaluated digital entrepreneurship and its effect on digital supply chains: The mediating function of business intelligence applications in Jordan. The study population comprised (835) male and female employees, and a simple random sample of (342) participants was used in conjunction with the descriptive-analytical method. To achieve the objectives of the study, a developed questionnaire was used to collect data from the sample members. The study adopted the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS. V. 22) and Structural Equations Modeling (SEM) using the AMOS program for path analysis and to perform statistical analysis. The most important results of the study were: the presence of an important impact of Digital Entrepreneurship in digital supply chains and the presence of a significant impact of Digital Entrepreneurship through business intelligence applications.

Omoyele, Babarinde, Adeleke, and Aigbedion (2022) examined digital entrepreneurship and sustainable business models: evidence amongst SMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted in the study. Three hundred and eighty-seven small and medium enterprise managers were surveyed. The results were analyzed using regression analysis. The analysis revealed that in addressing the study's first objective, the findings revealed that most of the digital entrepreneurs in Lagos State are ground-up digital entrepreneurs. The empirical result indicated that digital technologies provide unique combinations of sustainable business model components such as integrated value proposition, comprehensive value creation, and multifaceted value capture.

Srouf and Azmy (2021) examined inventory management and its impact on the firm performance in Egypt. This study investigated how inventory turnover, which measures inventory management, affects a firm's performance, which is determined by profitability using return on equity and return on assets. The Egyptian stock exchange

market provided the data. EViews 12 was used for both multiple regression and descriptive statistics in the analysis of this study. The study's findings, which were deemed statistically significant at the 5% level, showed a positive association between inventory turnover and return on assets ($R^2= 0.769321$) as well as return on equity ($R^2= 0.669593$).

Tarhini, Alalwan, Shammout, and Al-Badi (2020) examined the factors affecting mobile commerce adoption in developing countries: Towards an integrated model in Oman. A conceptual framework combination of elements from SERVQUAL (system quality, service quality, and information quality) and UTAUT2 (performance expectancy, expectancy effort, social influence, enabling conditions, hedonistic incentive, price value, habit, and self-efficacy). Information was gathered from 530 Omani m-commerce customers by a cross-sectional survey. The findings demonstrated that in order of influencing strength, performance expectancy, information quality, habit, trust, hedonistic incentive, service quality, pricing value, and facilitating conditions all had a substantial impact on customers' behavioural intention (BI) towards adopting m-commerce. A sixty-five percent of the variance BI was unaffected significantly by effort expectation, social influence, self-efficacy, and system quality.

Gap in Literature

A significant research gap exists in the current literature, encompassing methodological, variable, geographical, and temporal disparities. Previous studies exhibit differences in methodology, variables, location, and time frame, leaving a knowledge deficit relevant to this investigation. This study addresses these deficiencies, bridging the gaps by providing new insights through its unique approach.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to collect firsthand data from respondents through a structured questionnaire. The design enabled the collection of primary data, providing insights into the research variables. The study utilized simple random sampling to select participants, ensuring a representative sample from the population. The study used a census approach where data were collected from the entire population of 150 entrepreneurs or owners of registered SMEs in Anambra State under the National Association of Small-Scale Industrialists, Anambra State Chapter (2024). The population is from Onitsha, Nnewi, and Awka which are the three major cities in Anambra State representing the three senatorial zones of Anambra State; 50 entrepreneurs from Onitsha, Anambra North zone, 50 entrepreneurs from Nnewi, Anambra South zone and 50 entrepreneurs from Awka, Anambra Central zone, making the total population 150. The reason is to allow comprehensive data collection and analysis and to ensure geographic diversity and adequate representation of entrepreneurial perspectives across the state. The list of these enterprises based on zones can be seen in Appendix 1. To test the hypotheses, the study employed the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistical analysis tool on Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS). The significance level is set at 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Data Related to Research Questions

Decision Rule:

The decision in this analysis section is determined by the average of the responses of respondents. Strongly Agreed (5 points), Agreed (4 points), Disagreed (3 points), Strongly Disagreed (2 points) and Undecided (1 point). The average of the responses:

$$\frac{5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1}{5} = 3.0$$

Therefore, a mean score below 3.0 would be considered as rejected and a mean score of 3.0 and above would be considered as accepted.

Table 1: Research Question 1: What is the relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria?

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Remark
1	My business's reliance on mobile technology has improved our order management efficiency.	150	3.21	Accepted
2	I use mobile commerce to monitor my business's sales performance daily.	150	1.14	Rejected
3	Adopting mobile technology has helped my business reduce operating costs.	150	3.10	Accepted
4	My business has not seen a reduction in delivery errors since adopting mobile commerce solutions.	150	3.02	Accepted
5	I find it difficult to manage customer relationships and build loyalty through mobile platforms.	150	2.33	Rejected
6	Mobile commerce has improved communication between my business and my suppliers.	150	4.38	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 presents the findings related to the first research question, exploring the relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. A significant majority of respondents affirmed this connection, as evidenced by items 1, 3, 4, and 6, which garnered mean ratings exceeding the criterion mean of 3.0. Conversely, items 2 and 5 fell below this threshold. Overall, the data analysis reveals a positive correlation between mobile commerce adoption and lead time reduction among SMEs in the region, suggesting that mobile commerce can be a valuable tool in streamlining operations and enhancing efficiency.

Table 2: Research Question 2: What is the relationship between networking and inventory turnover of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria?

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Remark
1	My business benefits from collaborating with other SMEs to manage inventory efficiently.	150	3.33	Accepted
2	Networking allows my business to access bulk purchase discounts that improve inventory costs.	150	3.50	Accepted
3	My business does not rely on its network to keep up with industry trends that impact inventory turnover.	150	2.10	Rejected
4	My business has enhanced its inventory turnover rate by partnering with other SMEs for shared storage solutions.	150	1.88	Rejected
5	Networking with industry experts has not helped my business optimise its stock levels.	150	3.24	Accepted
6	My business leverages industry connections to source products quickly when needed.	150	4.11	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 investigates the relationship between networking and inventory turnover among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. The data analysis reveals a significant positive correlation, with items 1, 2, 5, and 6 exceeding the criterion mean of 3.0. Conversely, items 3 and 4 fell below this threshold. Overall, the majority of respondents affirm that networking has a substantial impact on inventory turnover, suggesting that effective networking strategies can enhance inventory management and efficiency among SMEs in the region.

Hypotheses Testing

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate if $P\text{-value} < 0.05$; if otherwise, accept the null Hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

Table 3

Ho: There is no significant relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ha: There is a significant relationship between mobile commerce and lead time reduction of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

		Mobile Commerce	Lead Reduction	Time
	Pearson correlation	1	.655**	
Mobile Commerce	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	
	N	150	150	
	Pearson correlation	.655**	1	
Lead Reduction	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		
	N	150	150	

Source: SPSS Output.

Table 3 reveals a statistically significant positive correlation between mobile commerce adoption and lead time reduction among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.655$) indicates a strong positive relationship, supported by a large sample size ($n = 150$) and a highly significant p-value ($p < 0.001$). Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted, confirming that mobile commerce has a profound impact on reducing lead times among SMEs in the region.

Hypothesis Two

Table 4

Ho: There is no significant relationship between networking and inventory turnover of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Ha: There is no significant relationship between networking and inventory turnover of small and medium enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria.

		Networking	Inventory Turnover
	Pearson correlation	1	.820**
Networking	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
	Pearson correlation	.820**	1
Inventory Turnover	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

Source: SPSS Output.

Table 4 reveals a robust positive correlation between networking and inventory turnover among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. The strong Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.820$) signifies a highly significant relationship, supported by a substantial sample size ($n = 150$) and an extremely low p-value ($p < 0.000$). This finding unequivocally supports the alternate hypothesis, confirming that effective networking significantly enhances inventory turnover among SMEs in the region.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings showed a statistically significant positive relationship between mobile commerce adoption and lead time reduction among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. This is in agreement with the findings of Tarhini, Alalwan, Shammout, and Al-Badi (2020), in their study on analysis of the factors affecting mobile commerce adoption in developing countries: Towards an integrated model in Oman. This implies that mobile commerce adoption significantly reduces lead times and enhances operational efficiency and competitiveness.

Results further revealed a robust positive correlation between networking and inventory turnover among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. This concurs with the results of Srouf and Azmy (2021) in their study on inventory management and its impact on firm performance in Egypt. This implies that networking significantly boosts inventory turnover, enhancing operational efficiency and profitability for SMEs in Anambra State, Nigeria.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

1. There is a statistically significant positive correlation between mobile commerce adoption and lead time reduction among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria.
2. There is a positive significant relationship between networking and inventory turnover among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study conclusively established a strong, statistically significant link between digital business models, entrepreneurship, and effective supply chain management among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. This finding implies that embracing digital transformation and entrepreneurial strategies can significantly enhance SMEs' supply chain efficiency, reduce operational costs, and foster competitiveness, ultimately driving business growth and economic development in the region.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Anambra State SMEs need to adopt mobile commerce by integrating mobile payments, logistics tracking, and e-commerce platforms to reduce lead times and boost efficiency.
2. Anambra State SMEs need to cultivate strategic networking through conferences, workshops, and industry associations to enhance inventory turnover and boost business performance.

Contribution to knowledge

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing empirical evidence of the significant relationships between digital business models, entrepreneurship (mobile commerce and networking), and supply chain management (lead time reduction and inventory turnover) among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the findings highlight the potential of mobile commerce adoption in streamlining operations and reducing costs, while strategic networking enhances inventory turnover. This research

fills a geographical gap in existing literature, providing insights into the Nigerian context and informing policymakers, entrepreneurs, and SME managers on effective digital strategies to improve operational efficiency, competitiveness, and sustainable business growth in the region.

Suggestions for Further Study

1. Further research should investigate the impact of digital strategies on other aspects of SME performance, such as financial performance, innovation, and employee productivity, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of their benefits.
2. Additionally, comparative studies examining the effectiveness of digital strategies across different regions, industries, and firm sizes would provide valuable insights into context-specific challenges and opportunities for SME growth.

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